

Impossible Fibers Axiovert A1 Fluorescence Imaging Guide

Model: Axiovert A1 TL/FL Inverted Fluorescence Microscope

Version: 1.0

Author: Sarah Hunt

This document has notes on how to set up the microscope to take fluorescence microscopy images. It is current as of 12/17/2025.

Process

1. Turn on the lamp next to the microscope to start it warming up. It will take about 30 minutes to be ready for use, so you can use this time to finish prepping samples.
2. When ready, turn on the microscope. The power button is on the lower left side. This will most likely start the microscope in brightfield view - if white light is shining through the stage, this means the brightfield light is on.
3. When ready for fluorescence, start by turning off the brightfield light. Do this by spinning the wheel on the lower right side all the way towards you (counterclockwise). This should make your view go entirely black.
4. Flip the light switch to fluorescence mode. This is the lever on the lower left side. Move it up to the cross symbol.
5. Make sure the lamp is set at the intensity you want. (You can change this with the up and down symbols on the lamp controller.)
6. Select the appropriate fluorescence filter by spinning the lower tan wheel below the stage. Filter 1 is DAPI, filter 2 is GFP, and filter 3 is RFP. Filter 4 is no filter.
7. Hit the "Start/stop" button on the lamp controller. The light next to "open" should turn green - this means the fluorescence light is passing through to the microscope.
8. If you have the GFP filter selected, you should see blue light shining on your slide. If you have the RFP filter selected, you should see green light shining on your slide. If DAPI is selected you won't see any light - it excites in UV.
9. To capture images on the computer, make sure the Zen software is on, and that you have the black slider in the front pulled out - look for the camera vs eye symbols.
10. In the Zen software, if everything looks really black, take a look at the histogram, and adjust the levels. (Of course, if you don't have anything fluorescent, it should look completely black). Also, you'll get better contrast by blocking out ambient light above the slide.
11. When you're done, make sure to flip the switch back to brightfield and turn the light back on by spinning the dial on the lower right. Also make sure to turn the lamp off since it will burn out the longer it runs. Just remember that it has a cooling off period, so if you turn it off you won't be able to turn it back on again for a while.